

Creation and Implementation of BIM Model Measurement Rules

MOHAMMAD ASIM

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Abstract

The approach of Building Information Modelling (BIM) is characterised by collaborative workflows and information exchange, which allows for the automation of procedures and ultimately improves productivity. BIM models serve as centralised databases of data that may be used for a variety of tasks, including project cost estimation at various stages. Although BIM offers numerous benefits, the process of accurately estimating costs is still challenging since it requires the use of standardised measurement criteria and dependable construction cost databases. This research tackles these problems by formulating a set of measurement rules specifically designed for the BIM environment. The purpose of these rules is to simplify the process of determining quantities and improve the accuracy of the bill of quantities (BOQ). This will help to minimise the possibility of human error that is often present in older methods.

The main goal of this research is to develop a strong set of general measurement rules that can be smoothly incorporated into an automated workflow for estimating building costs. Open-BIM Quantities software created by CYPE (a software development company) is used in this work for creating and implementing the general measurement rules. The workflow presented

in this work incorporates several essential stages, such as defining a work breakdown structure, creating the modelling rules including the level of information need for BIM models, extracting quantities from the BIM model, creating and implementing the general measurement rules, utilising a building cost database, and providing a bill of quantities. Additionally, case studies are utilised to verify the efficacy of the suggested workflow. These case studies exemplify the actual use of the approach in real-life situations, showcasing enhancements in the accuracy of cost estimation and the efficiency of the process.

The results suggest that including standardised measurement rules into the BIM framework greatly improves the precision of BOQs. The automated approach not only saves time on preparation, but it also ensures that final estimates are more accurate. The generated information becomes more coherent, hence enhancing decision-making and project management. However, the research also acknowledges several limitations, including the need for intensive training associated with putting BIM techniques into practice. Thus, one of the research's future directions is to broaden the scope of the measurement criteria to include a greater range of building elements and project classifications. To promote greater industry adoption, it is recommended to enhance the compatibility of BIM tools with other construction management software.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/blQXZT5fwFM>

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